

Dynamic Reconfiguration of Deep Neural Networks for Resource-Constrained FPGA Edge Accelerators

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Abstract—Executing resource intensive Deep Neural Networks (DNN) on resource constrained devices at the edge provides many benefits. Executing DNN at the edge reduces latency by processing data locally without the overhead of Cloud communications. This is critical for real-time or near real-time applications such as autonomous vehicles or critical IoT systems. Execution of DNN at the edge also enhances privacy by processing private data at the edge, and reducing the need to send sensitive data over the network. It also reduces bandwidth usage by minimizing data transfer and preserves network resources. It also contributes to increased autonomy and resilience of edge devices that can continue to operate when disconnected from the network. And finally by optimizing DNN for the edge, it allows DNN to operate within power constraints of the edge while maintaining performance. Achieving these benefits requires solving a number of research challenges related to resource constraints at the edge, model compression and optimization for the edge, latency and real-time processing, hardware-software co-design, scalability and flexibility, and development and deployment complexity. To be able to process complex DNN at the edge, hardware acceleration with FPGA is a very promising approach. FPGA can be easily customised for a given DNN architecture, they provide high performance, can be configured to be more power efficient than GPU, and can be reconfigured for different DNN providing much needed flexibility. To address the above challenges, this paper proposes combining Edge orchestration techniques with DNN design frameworks that are able to accelerate the network design phase, optimize the DNN for the underlying edge devices in terms of size and energy, and convert the DNN to FPGA implementations providing hardware acceleration benefits at the edge.

Index Terms—Edge FPGA, DeepEdgeSoC framework, DNN deployment, DMWay, orchestration

I. INTRODUCTION

FPGA (System on Chip - Field Programmable Gate Array) SoCs offer a particularly interesting solution for the implementation of neural networks. This combination of processor and programmable logic fabric makes it possible to combine the flexibility of software with the performance of dedicated hardware.

The reconfigurable programmable logic allows the hardware structure to be tailored to a neural network’s specific algorithm, optimizing execution speed and resource consumption. In addition, FPGAs enable a high degree of parallelism, which is ideal for neural networks that require many simultaneous computations, such as convolutions in Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The energy efficiency makes them a relevant choice for embedded systems or real-time devices.

The processor (such as ARM Cortex) handles control and management tasks, as well as data pre- and post-processing. For example, it can handle the acquisition of input data, its formatting and normalization before transmitting it to the FPGA logic units for neural network calculations. Once the calculation results are obtained, the processor can also process the output data to transmit it to the system appropriately. In addition, the processor is used to manage the configuration and dynamic reprogramming of the FPGA, thus optimizing resources according to the application needs.

This division of tasks between the processor and the FPGA ensures increased flexibility, allowing the implementation of various neural network architectures with improved efficiency and reduced energy consumption which meets the requirements of Edge Computing.

The operational flexibility required by Edge Computing applications combined with the limitation of hardware resources requires intelligent control of these. Thus, the embedded system must be able to dynamically reconfigure its processing resources, such as programmable logic neural networks, as the operating steps evolve. This requires centralized software management of tasks.

The paper is structured as follows: in Section 2, we expose the main challenges and how they will be . In Section 3, we provide technical details about each component our proposal. Section 4 provides some initial results. Lastly, we discuss futures work and perspectives in section 5.

II. RELATED WORKS AND RESEARCH CHALLENGES

Training and deploying deep neural networks (DNNs) on FPGAs for edge devices/platforms raises several research challenges:

- **Resource Constraints:** FPGAs on edge platforms have limited memory, power, and computational resources compared to cloud environments. Efficient use of these limited resources by DNNs is critical.
- **Model Compression and Optimization:** Techniques like quantization, pruning, knowledge distillation, low-rank factorization or weight sharing and clustering are essential to reduce model size while retaining sufficient accuracy, as large models may not fit or function efficiently on FPGAs.
- **Latency and Real-Time Processing:** Edge applications often require real-time or low-latency processing. Optimizing DNNs for minimal inference delay while managing hardware constraints is challenging. This can involve using the above mentioned model optimization techniques, FPGA specific optimization (hardware parallelism, data flow optimization, efficient memory management) and hardware-software co-design so that the DNN and FPGA configurations work seamlessly together.
- **Hardware-Software Co-Design:** Integrating software (DNN architectures) with FPGA hardware requires close collaboration to optimize performance. This includes balancing dataflow, memory access, and parallel computation.
- **Scalability and Flexibility:** Unlike GPUs, FPGAs are less flexible when switching between different DNN architectures. Ensuring that the FPGA setup is adaptable to evolving DNN models is an ongoing challenge. This is especially true in the case of shared edge resources where resources are shared between tenants and have to be reconfigured quickly.
- **Development and Deployment Complexity:** FPGAs require specialized knowledge for programming (e.g., using VHDL or high-level synthesis tools), which can hinder rapid prototyping and deployment.

These challenges require novel methods in model design, hardware optimization, and software toolchains to make FPGAs viable for deep learning on edge devices or multi-tenant edge platforms with shared resources.

This paper addresses the above research challenges in the following way:

- for the "Resource Constraints" challenge, it defines a method to train and deploy DNN on low cost FPGA boards with limited resources. This approach is key to bringing the benefits of DNN hardware acceleration for edge devices/platforms, while limiting the costs of the FPGA resources. The work also addresses the challenge by dynamically reconfiguring the FPGA board so that it can be shared by different DNN.
- for the "Model Compression and Optimization" challenge, it proposes using DNN quantization and compres-

sion techniques to reduce the memory and computational requirements of a DNN for edge devices with limited memory and energy resources while monitoring quantization accuracy degradation.

- for the "Latency and Real-Time Processing" challenge, the paper proposes orchestration of the DNN deployment and FPGA reconfiguration process to meet latency and real-time processing requirements. In particular when several DNN have to be executed in sequence on a shared FPGA with near real-time constraints, the edge middleware orchestrator monitors DNN inference quality and triggers reconfiguration of the FPGA for the next DNN in the sequence.
- for the "Hardware-Software Co-Design" challenge, the paper provides support for designing DNN with near real-time constraints so that they can be deployed on dynamically reconfigurable edge FPGA with limited resources
- for the "Scalability and Flexibility" challenge, the paper proposes an on-demand FPGA reconfiguration approach so that several DNN can be executed in sequence on a shared edge FPGA. The current paper assumes that a single edge FPGA resource is available per application. The case of multiple FPGA resources on an edge platform that can be used to parallelize or scale the DNN is left for future work.
- for the "Development and Deployment Complexity" challenge, the paper combines middleware orchestrator techniques with a DNN design and deployment environment that supports FPGA hardware acceleration. This allows to provide integrated support for both the design and execution phases of a DNN on edge device/platform FPGA, and support on demand FPGA reconfiguration.

In the literature, most works focus on two main themes: model compression and efficient hardware architecture design, aiming to optimize FPGA resource utilization. For instance, [1] research emphasizes FPGA acceleration to enhance computational efficiency and reduce resource usage in deep neural networks, particularly convolutional neural networks (CNNs), in edge computing scenarios. Techniques such as model compression and hardware reconfiguration are explored to enable energy-efficient deployment on devices like the Xilinx KV260 FPGA platform. [2] study presents a dynamically reconfigurable FPGA-based CNN accelerator designed to address the challenges of limited hardware resources and energy inefficiency. It emphasizes leveraging advanced architectural strategies and model quantization techniques to enhance FPGA performance, enabling efficient execution of tasks like real-time object detection and AI inference on edge devices. [3] explores hardware and data optimization techniques for deploying deep neural networks on FPGA platforms with constrained edge environments. It highlights key strategies such as enhancing memory bandwidth utilization, minimizing communication overhead, and applying design-space exploration to achieve an optimal balance between performance and energy efficiency. As detailed in the challenges section, our

proposal combines the optimization of FPGA resources and an orchestration of dynamic DNN deployment to optimize the resource allocation. In the next section we will detail each step and we will validate our approach with a car plate detection use case.

III. SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

A. Case study: Car plate recognition application

In order to illustrate and validate our approach, we will base our explanations/analysis on the implementation of a license plate recognition application. This application is implemented in two steps. The first step consists of detecting a license plate in an image and taking a snapshot of it. the second step consists of recognizing the characters on the license plate and saving the obtained results.

Figure 1 illustrates how the application works. Each of the two steps requires the exploitation of a neural network. Step 1 exploits the license plate detection network named **D-Net**. Step 2 uses the license plate recognition network named **R-Net**

Fig. 1. Car plate recognition use-case

DMWay monitors the application in order to watch the size of D-Net bounding boxes. When the bonding box reaches the ideal size which guarantees that the license plate has been correctly detected, a snapshot is taken. This triggers the reconfiguration of the FPGA for the execution of the second step. The deployment of R-Net is executed using the DeepEdgeSoC [4] framework, and has as input the image detected by D-Net. Finally, the result of R-Net is sent to DMWay in order to store it in database.

The advantage of the DMWay orchestration is that it is set up by configuration. The graphical user interface allows to define the two steps of the processing to be executed based on events or jobs. This flexibility avoids code modifications and facilitates the application of the same principle to other use cases..

B. DMWay Orchestration

DMway is an edge middleware that manages monitoring of data from sources of different types. Data sources can correspond to IoT data as well as application data. In this paper the middleware is used for application data monitoring and on-demand neural network orchestration. By on demand orchestration we mean the triggering of neural network deployment only when it is required. Indeed, in order to optimize

the use of an FPGA card resources, it is relevant to exploit all these resources at a time to execute only one of the neural networks involved thus resources are not allocated uselessly.

The switching from one neural network to another is managed according to the specification of the application implemented and the triggering mechanism. When the trigger is received by DMWay, a new neural network deployment starts. This on-demand deployment is made possible thanks to the DeepEdgeSoC framework, detailed in the next section, that reconfigures the FPGA for the deployment of the next DNN.

Figure 2 shows the DMWay toolbox components involved in this work. It is a modular and flexible approach providing the ability to orchestrate tasks by configuration, which makes it easy to set up the control of the neural network as well as the required processing on the input data.

Fig. 2. DMWay toolbox overview

To ensure the monitoring we exploit the concept of JOBS. A job can be seen as a piece of code (it can be a conditional task, a shell command, etc.) dedicated to carrying out a specific task. It is possible de set up different jobs depending on the tasks that we have to deal with. The result of a job is used as a trigger by the orchestration mechanism.

C. FPGA Design Flow

Although DMWay is responsible for orchestrating two different networks, the design procedure for both networks is the same. In this subsection, we describe the general design methodology for designing and deploying a neural network on FPGA SoC. Then in the next subsection, we explain the architecture of each network separately. The end-to-end design flow leverages the integrated DeepEdgeSoC [4] framework, as can be seen in Figure 3. The first step involves preparing the dataset for training and evaluating the network. Afterwards, the network architecture is designed to perform the task assigned to it. The dataset is used to train the network by providing the input images and the corresponding groundtruth and running the network loop for a defined number of epochs. When the training is done, the network performance can be validated using an unseen part of the dataset.

To ensure the entire network fits onto the FPGA fabric, the 32-bit floating-point parameters and activations must be quantized i.e., converted to a more compact fixed-point format. A quick post-training quantization (PTQ) method is often effective, where quantization is applied after training. However, if accuracy degradation is significant, we employ quantization-aware training (QAT). DeepEdgeSoC, using PyTorch, enables

Fig. 3. End-to-end FPGA-based neural network design flow

exploration of various bit-width combinations for optimized quantization.

Once the quantized network reaches the desired accuracy, it needs to be converted into a format that can be synthesized for the FPGA. To facilitate this, DeepEdgeSoC generates a hardware-optimized C++ implementation of the network that can be fed into Vitis HLS. The resulting IP Core is imported by Vivado HLS for the system integration. This is where the interfaces between the different SoC parts are configured. This design process produces an individual bitstream file for each network utilized in this work.

D. Neural Network Design

In this subsection, the architectural details of both D-Net and R-Net are outlined. This includes descriptions of their respective structures, key layers, and the mechanisms enabling their specific functionalities.

1) *License Plate Detection Network (D-Net)*: Detecting license plates involves locating and identifying a license plate in an image. This task can be formulated as an object detection problem. D-Net is designed as a variant of Single-Shot Detector (SSD) network. Specifically, D-Net is a single fully convolutional neural network (FCN) comprising of a backbone feature extractor and two heads for classification and localization. The feature extractor backbone consists of two components: a downscale part and a multiscale part. The downscale part reduces the spatial dimensions of the input using a chain of convolutional and pooling layers. On the other hand, the multiscale part is essential for enhancing the network’s ability to detect license plates of different sizes and scales. As with SSD, D-Net localizes license plates by predicting relative to predefined bounding boxes (anchors). During training, the groundtruth bounding boxes $(x_{min}, y_{min}, x_{max}, y_{max})$ are encoded to simplify the training process. Contrariwise, the predicted bounding boxes are decoded during inference to restore the original localization values. The network performs binary classification, as there are only two classes: license plate and background. The output size of the network depends on the number of anchors (n) and is independent of the number of license plates in the image. Precisely, the localization output is $4 \times n$ (since each bounding box is specified by 4 values), while the binary classification output is $2 \times n$ (corresponding

to the two classes for each anchor). These raw outputs must be post-processed in order to obtain meaningful results. The post-processing includes decoding the outputs then matching with anchors, eliminating undesired outputs by thresholding the classification scores, and applying Non-Maximum Suppression (NMS) to remove duplicated detections.

2) *License Plate Recognition Network (R-Net)*: The European car license plates consist of a variable number of characters, normally between 4 and 8, which are centered along the width of the license plate and therefore are not always presented at fixed positions. It is important to point out that in license plate recognition, the focus is on identifying the characters correctly in the proper left-to-right order regardless of their exact position on the plate. Therefore, an object detection network is not required. We design a Convolutional Recurrent Neural Network (CRNN) for license plate recognition, consisting of 3 parts as shown in figure 4. The first part is a CNN responsible for extracting the features from license plate input image. The CNN consists of three convolutional layers, each followed by a batch normalization and ReLU activation layers and each having a kernel size of (3×3) and a stride of 1. The features coming from the first and the second convolutional layers are down-sampled using (2×2) max-pooling layers. Afterwards, the feature maps, which have the size (B, C, H, W) , are reshaped into an equivalent tensor of shape $(B, W, C \times H)$, which corresponds the shape $(Batch_size, sequence_length, input_size)$ that the LSTM layer expects its input to be of. The hidden size of the LSTM layer is 32. Finally, a single linear layer is used as the final step to translate the LSTM sequential output into a prediction that corresponds to the character classes. To ensure the network ability to handle inputs of arbitrary size, the input is resized to a fixed size (60×320) .

Fig. 4. License plate recognition network (R-Net)

IV. EXPERIMENTS AND RESULTS

In this section, we first introduce the datasets used in this work, then we highlight the experimental setup for training and testing the proposed network and the corresponding preliminary results. In the current phase of our work, we have trained and evaluated R-Net. The training and evaluation of D-Net will be conducted in future work as part of the ongoing development of this project.

A. Datasets

In this subsection, the datasets used to train the neural networks are introduced.

Fig. 5. Synthetic license plates with random characters. Augmentation includes skewing, random noise and blur.

1) *License Plate Detection Dataset*: The License Plate Detection Dataset [5] contains an annotated collection of diverse car images with varying sizes containing one or more license plates. The dataset consists of 4295 training samples and 1073 validation samples. In order to increase the training quality, the images are taken from various angles and lighting conditions. Each image is provided with a corresponding annotation file that includes class labels and bounding box coordinates for each license plate in the image. It should be noted that this dataset does not include labels for the characters on the license plates, focusing instead on detecting plate locations without character-level annotation.

2) *License Plate Recognition Dataset*: In order to train R-Net, an annotated dataset of cropped license plate images is required. One way to obtain this dataset is to manually annotate cropped license plates from the previous dataset. However, this process is tedious and time-consuming. Alternatively, we generate a synthetic annotated license plate dataset containing 20K images, where each image file is saved under the name of the license plate characters. Figure 5 illustrates some samples from the generated dataset. The dataset is partitioned into 90% for training and 10% for testing. The first step in creating this data set is to design empty white and yellow license plate to be used as templates. Afterwards, these templates are used to generate license plate images by writing a random character sequence of random length (4 to 8) using the standard FE-Schrift font. The dataset images are augmented by applying Gaussian blur, random salt-and-pepper noise, and random left and right skew. These augmentations help the model generalize better by simulating real-world variations in image quality and orientation.

B. Experimental Setup

We use NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 to train R-Net using the training configurations in Table I. The network is trained for 100 epochs with a batch size of 64 using Adam optimizer with a learning rate of 0.01. The loss function used for the recognition task is Connectionist Temporal Classification (CTC) Loss. This loss function is particularly suitable for recognition tasks involving sequential data, such as text from license plates, because it aligns predicted sequences with ground truth without requiring explicit frame-level alignment. Furthermore, it allows the network to handle variable-length sequences and can predict outputs with blank tokens.

C. Preliminary Results

The trained R-Net achieved 97% accuracy on the unseen dataset test split, which indicates its ability to detect license plates with high reliability. The accuracy was evaluated by

TABLE I
TRAINING CONFIGURATION FOR R-NET

Configuration	Value
Input Channel number	3
Total Training Epochs	100
Input Size	60 × 320
Batch Size	64
Optimizer	Adam
Learning Rate	0.01
Data Augmentation	Gaussian Blur - Random Noise - Random Skew
Loss Function	CTC Loss

counting the number of correct predictions as a percentage of the total number of predictions. In other words, if the ground truth exactly equals the prediction, it contributes to the correct count, which is then divided by the total number of samples, as shown in Equation 1.

$$\text{Accuracy} = \frac{\text{Number of Correct Predictions}}{\text{Total Number of Predictions}} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

V. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORKS

In this work, we highlighted the benefits of deploying Deep Neural Networks (DNNs) on resource-constrained edge devices, including reduced latency and enhanced privacy. Achieving these benefits requires overcoming challenges such as model optimization, energy efficiency, and real-time processing constraints. The capabilities of DMWay orchestration middleware are demonstrated through a car license plate recognition case study. The implementation is divided into two stages: license plate detection and license plate recognition. Using DeepEdgeSoC framework, we design a separate neural network for each stage, namely the license plate detection network (D-Net) and the license plate recognition network (R-Net).

In future work, the focus will be on training D-Net to detect license plates accurately. Additionally, both D-Net and R-Net will be quantized to reduce the size of both networks for a negligible drop in accuracy. Eventually, the networks must be synthesized to run on the edge FPGA SoC platform chosen for this work. In parallel, the DMWay orchestration will be finalized, tested, and validated, followed by integration work to coordinate all components of the global solution.

REFERENCES

- [1] K. Choi and G. E. Sobelman, "An efficient cnn accelerator for low-cost edge systems," *ACM Trans. Embed. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 21, Aug. 2022.
- [2] K. Choi and G. E. Sobelman, "An efficient cnn accelerator for low-cost edge systems," *ACM Trans. Embed. Comput. Syst.*, vol. 21, Aug. 2022.
- [3] X. Liu, D. H. Kim, C. Wu, and O. Chen, "Resource and data optimization for hardware implementation of deep neural networks targeting fpga-based edge devices," in *2018 ACM/IEEE International Workshop on System Level Interconnect Prediction (SLIP)*, pp. 1–8, 2018.
- [4] M. R. Al Koutayni, G. Reis, and D. Stricker, "Deepedgesoc: End-to-end deep learning framework for edge iot devices," *Internet of Things*, vol. 21, p. 100665, 2023.
- [5] F. Elmenshawii, "License plate detection dataset." <https://www.kaggle.com/datasets/fareselmenshawii/license-plate-dataset>, 2021. Accessed: 2024-11-14.

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